

CERTIFICATION PAGE

Certification for Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant:

By signing and submitting this proposal, the individual applicant or the authorized official of the applicant institution is: (1) certifying that statements made herein are true and complete to the best of his/her knowledge; and (2) agreeing to accept the obligation to comply with NSF award terms and conditions if an award is made as a result of this application. Further, the applicant is hereby providing certifications regarding debarment and suspension, drug-free workplace, and lobbying activities (see below), as set forth in Grant Proposal Guide (GPG), NSF 02-2. Willful provision of false information in this application and its supporting documents or in reports required under an ensuing award is a criminal offense (U. S. Code, Title 18, Section 1001).

In addition, if the applicant institution employs more than fifty persons, the authorized official of the applicant institution is certifying that the institution has implemented a written and enforced conflict of interest policy that is consistent with the provisions of Grant Policy Manual Section 510; that to the best of his/her knowledge, all financial disclosures required by that conflict of interest policy have been made; and that all identified conflicts of interest will have been satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated prior to the institution's expenditure of any funds under the award, in accordance with the institution's conflict of interest policy. Conflicts which cannot be satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated must be disclosed to NSF.

Drug Free Work Place Certification

By electronically signing the NSF Proposal Cover Sheet, the Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant is providing the Drug Free Work Place Certification contained in Appendix A of the Grant Proposal Guide.

Debarment and Suspension Certification

(If answer "yes", please provide explanation.)

Is the organization or its principals presently debarred, suspended, proposed for debarment, declared ineligible, or voluntarily excluded from covered transactions by any Federal department or agency?

Yes

No

By electronically signing the NSF Proposal Cover Sheet, the Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant is providing the Debarment and Suspension Certification contained in Appendix B of the Grant Proposal Guide.

Certification Regarding Lobbying

This certification is required for an award of a Federal contract, grant, or cooperative agreement exceeding \$100,000 and for an award of a Federal loan or a commitment providing for the United States to insure or guarantee a loan exceeding \$150,000.

Certification for Contracts, Grants, Loans and Cooperative Agreements

The undersigned certifies, to the best of his or her knowledge and belief, that:

(1) No federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid, by or on behalf of the undersigned, to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with the awarding of any federal contract, the making of any Federal grant, the making of any Federal loan, the entering into of any cooperative agreement, and the extension, continuation, renewal, amendment, or modification of any Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement.

(2) If any funds other than Federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with this Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement, the undersigned shall complete and submit Standard Form-LLL, "Disclosure of Lobbying Activities," in accordance with its instructions.

(3) The undersigned shall require that the language of this certification be included in the award documents for all subawards at all tiers including subcontracts, subgrants, and contracts under grants, loans, and cooperative agreements and that all subrecipients shall certify and disclose accordingly.

This certification is a material representation of fact upon which reliance was placed when this transaction was made or entered into. Submission of this certification is a prerequisite for making or entering into this transaction imposed by section 1352, Title 31, U.S. Code. Any person who fails to file the required certification shall be subject to a civil penalty of not less than \$10,000 and not more than \$100,000 for each such failure.

AUTHORIZED ORGANIZATIONAL REPRESENTATIVE		SIGNATURE	DATE
NAME Wendy K Warnick		Electronic Signature	Aug 21 2002 12:07AM
TELEPHONE NUMBER 907-474-1600	ELECTRONIC MAIL ADDRESS warnick@arcus.org		FAX NUMBER 907-474-1604

*SUBMISSION OF SOCIAL SECURITY NUMBERS IS VOLUNTARY AND WILL NOT AFFECT THE ORGANIZATION'S ELIGIBILITY FOR AN AWARD. HOWEVER, THEY ARE AN INTEGRAL PART OF THE INFORMATION SYSTEM AND ASSIST IN PROCESSING THE PROPOSAL. SSN SOLICITED UNDER NSF ACT OF 1950, AS AMENDED.

SUMMARY OF PROPOSED WORK

This is a request for a supplement to ARCUS' cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation (No. OPP-0101279). The supplement of \$381,400 will support one new activity and will provide additional funding for five ongoing activities as part of the organizational support ARCUS provides to the U.S. Arctic science programs. These activities fall under the following major tasks identified in the cooperative agreement: 1) Arctic Community Science Planning; 2) NSF Arctic Sciences Section Coordination; 4) Information and Outreach; and 5) Core Support. Several of the activities described here coordinate research-focused community workshops and several provide editorial and publication support or preparation and distribution of information to assist NSF and the arctic research community. All of the activities support the community science planning process for the NSF Arctic Sciences Section or provide information and support for the conduct of Arctic research.

The proposed activities that require supplemental funding are summarized below. Activities not previously included in this cooperative agreement are marked *New*.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.4 *New* SEARCH Community Workshop

This supplemental funding will support the initial planning for a SEARCH science meeting, which may be held in Fall 2003. Planning activities will include information gathering and coordination of community discussions to develop goals and planned outcomes, and, based on these goals, determining the workshop or meeting format, identifying and inviting key participants, identifying potential venues, and making arrangements for the actual meeting location.

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

2.2 *ARCTIC SYSTEM SCIENCE PROGRAM COORDINATION*

2.2.3 **Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC) Science Management Office**

The HARC Science Management Office, located at and funded through ARCUS, proposes to undertake a new activity, the development of a special issue of the journal *ARCTIC* on "Human Dimensions Research in the Arctic." The HARC initiative has funded innovative research linking human and natural systems in the Arctic. Publicizing this work through peer-reviewed publications is an important way of demonstrating its scientific significance to the research community, thereby stimulating greater interest in the initiative as a whole. At the ARCSS All-Hands Workshop in Seattle, in February 2002, a group of HARC researchers met twice and developed a list of activities for promoting HARC. One recommendation was the publication of a special issue of an appropriate journal, to gather in one place a set of papers on various human-dimensions projects. The purpose of this issue would be threefold: 1) to encourage HARC PIs to publish their results in a journal that is widely read by Arctic researchers from many disciplines, 2) to create a highly visible and easily referenced collection of human-dimensions papers in order to stimulate further development of this type of interdisciplinary research, and 3) to demonstrate through examples the nature of human-dimensions research and the breadth of questions that it can address.

After some discussion, the HARC researchers decided that the journal *ARCTIC* would be most suitable for this special issue. It is widely read in Arctic research circles in many disciplines, it is multi-disciplinary so that the papers can take a variety of academic perspectives, and it is a high-quality, peer-reviewed journal. The HARC Science Management Office contacted the editor of *ARCTIC*, who was enthusiastic about the idea. Following discussions with the then-director of ARCSS, the SMO contacted the HARC PIs to solicit titles and abstracts for the special issue. Thirteen proposals have been received, indicating a strong commitment by the HARC research community to the idea. Manuscripts will be submitted to *ARCTIC* by the end of September 2002, with the goal of publishing the special 100-page issue in late 2003 or early 2004. To further encourage the papers' authors, the HARC SMO will pay for most or all of the page charges levied by *ARCTIC*. To use this issue for further HARC publicity, within and beyond the arctic research community, the SMO will purchase copies of the entire issue to distribute as appropriate.

2.3 *ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION*

2.3.1 **Planning for a Community Conference on Arctic Social Sciences Research**

ARCUS will follow the recommendations from the January 2001 workshop on arctic social sciences to work with the research community to plan a large community-wide conference in Spring 2003. Coordination activities include discussing conference focus, goals, and timing with the NSF Arctic Social Sciences Program Manager, selecting and convening a conference organizing committee, establishing a timeline, main topics, keynote speakers, and invited participants, and announcing the conference and publish a call for abstracts. Other activities will include the development of a web site and other online resources to promote discussion with members of the research community to identify critical areas and research priorities for further discussion. The conference will be convened in early 2003, bringing academic arctic researchers together with social scientists based in other regions, federal and state agency scientists, and policy and decision-makers working on related issues. The conference format will include sessions on a variety of topics, panel discussions, and a poster session, with ample opportunities for brainstorming and informal discussions.

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

4.1 ***Witness the Arctic: Chronicles of the Arctic Science Research Program***

Witness the Arctic has been published biannually since 1993 and provides information on current arctic research efforts and findings, significant research initiatives, national policy affecting arctic research, international activities, and profiles of institutions with major arctic research efforts. *Witness* currently serves an audience of over 8,500 arctic scientists, educators, agency personnel, and policy makers and is available both on-line and in print. The activities funded through this supplement include:

- Preparation, publication, and distribution of 8,500 copies of a 40-page issue of *Witness* by January 2002 (Winter 2002, Volume 10, Number 1). This request also supports publication of the newsletter on ARCUS' web site, <http://www.arcus.org>.
- Initial development work for the Spring 2003 issue of *Witness* (Volume 10, Number 2), which will be published in May 2003.

4.7 Publication: *The Arctic*

Many members of the arctic research community have expressed a need for an introduction to the environments and peoples of the Arctic that is scientifically accurate while remaining comprehensible to the general public, including middle and high school students. To address this need, ARCUS began developing an overview of the arctic region for a general audience in 2001, with funding through our previous cooperative agreement with NSF. Tentatively titled *The Arctic: Changes in a Polar Region*, this book will be similar to a magazine in quality of graphics and level of complexity and will be accessible to a wide range of readers. The contents and the publication design and layout are targeted to the general public and middle and high school students. The contents cover ocean, terrestrial, and human components of the Arctic and review various aspects of these domains, including contemporary and historical research, through a seasonal framework. Links among important arctic processes and between the biophysical systems and human cultures are illustrated. The draft publication was circulated for review in January 2001 by a selected group of educators, arctic researchers, and experts in science information development. The reviews provided substantive guidance for the difficult task of describing diverse and complex processes and simply and clearly. Because of the amount of work still required to create a publication of the quality considered necessary by ARCUS, NSF, and the research community, we delayed further work on this publication in order to direct staff resources to other more urgently needed projects. This supplemental funding requested here will support the completion of this important resource and the publication and distribution of 5,000 copies by March 2003.

5. CORE SUPPORT

Core support provides management and infrastructure crucial to support all major tasks and the projects and activities included in each task through the cooperative agreement. This category was initiated at the recommendation of the NSF program officer, who suggested that stability and continuity would be achieved more effectively by defining a category to support direct activities that support the whole of the cooperative agreement that would not be vulnerable to the changes in the specific tasks and activities funded from year-to-year through the cooperative agreement. The supplemental funds requested here will support ongoing activities in this category for January through March 2003.

ARCUS is a relatively small non-profit organization and the Executive Director is intimately involved in all activities of the organization including planning, prioritizing, managing, and directly implementing the work undertaken on behalf of the National Science Foundation. The Executive Director works closely with ARCUS project managers to prioritize tasks with respect to annual and longer-term plans and to manage individual workloads and projects. She closely reviews activities and products and ensures that projects are completed as scheduled and in accordance with the annual plan and that the products or effects of the activities are beneficial to arctic research and to the goals of the particular task funded through the cooperative agreement. She is directly involved in working with outside committees and contributors to ensure that projects are concluded effectively and in a timely fashion. The Executive Director also works closely with the ARCUS Business Manager in budgeting and reviewing ongoing project expenditures against the NSF budget. The Executive Director liaises directly with NSF on all planning, programmatic, and budget issues. This component of management is essential to the ongoing work ARCUS carries out on behalf of NSF.

Similarly, the Systems Administrator manages the network, server, and all technical needs required to support NSF tasks and sub-tasks. He works directly with the Executive Director to ensure that all hardware and software requirements are met so that server and network operations supporting NSF activities are carried out smoothly and efficiently. The Executive Director and Systems Administrator research and plan for upcoming needs, including scientific meetings and conferences convened by ARCUS on behalf of the NSF, in conjunction with the annual plan.

While the work of both these positions is directly related to the successful implementation of NSF activities and projects, it is more difficult to allocate much of this time specifically to any one individual project, hence the use of Core Support to collect these direct overarching management and infrastructure costs. Other costs charged to Core Support include direct system infrastructure (computer hardware and software required to maintain the network and server needed to support the database and listserver, NSF sponsored tasks), high-speed Internet lines, and the development necessary to continuously maintain the level of service committed to the Arctic research community under the cooperative agreement.

Activities supported during January through March 2003 will include:

- Coordinating planning, prioritization and supervision of work on the tasks and projects described in the program plan during this period in 2003. The portion of the Executive Director's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement will be charged to the Core Support category.
- Investigating and upgrading hardware, software and programming required to expand the capability of such projects as the Directory of Arctic Researchers, the ALIAS website, Arctic Info, the Calendar and NSF online program discussions, meeting registrations and poster submissions, and general information.
- Managing the server setup, the network, the creation of needed technical resources, and the computing capability that directly supports the project activities. The portion of the System Administrator's time dedicated to direct activities funded through this agreement will be charged to the Core Support category.

SUMMARY

ARCUS has facilitated scientific planning for arctic research efforts for over ten years by working with the scientific community through surveys, workshops, Internet communications, and other means to define science priorities and research initiatives. ARCUS has organized dozens of workshops and published numerous scientific planning documents, which reflect the recommendations of the arctic research community on scientific priorities in various research fields. All of the activities described in this request for supplemental funds support the community science planning process for the NSF Arctic Sciences Section and provide information and support for the conduct of Arctic research and, therefore, will contribute to the overall excellence and advancement of arctic research supported by the National Science Foundation.

JUSTIFICATION FOR THE SUPPLEMENT

This is a request for a supplement to ARCUS' cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation (No. OPP-0101279). The supplement of \$381,400 to the funding already awarded through No. OPP-0101279 is necessary because:

1. One activity described in this request, planning for a SEARCH community science meeting, is new and requires work beyond what was covered in the initial funding to ARCUS;
2. One activity, the support for a special issue of the journal *ARCTIC* on human dimensions research in the Arctic, is a new activity supported by the HARC Science Management Office, located at and funded through ARCUS;
3. An increase in the duration or level of activity in several ongoing projects requires additional funding.

All of the activities described here are in keeping with and part of ARCUS' work for the National Science Foundation (NSF), providing organizational support for the U.S. arctic science programs.

ARCUS is submitting this supplement request to undertake the new or additional activities at the request of and on behalf of the ARCSS Committee and the HARC Science Management Office, and in response to requests from the arctic social sciences research community, the SEARCH Interagency Working Group, and other participants in and managers of aspects of arctic research. The specific activities and the support that will be provided have been discussed with the relevant NSF Program Managers, as well.

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
Request for Supplemental Funding Year 2, Award OPP-0101279

1 ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.4 SEARCH Community Workshop

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	8,991
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	3,154
Participant Support Costs	-
Materials and Supplies	-
Publications/Dissemination	-
Consulting	-
Computer Services	-
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	2,000
Total direct costs	14,145
Indirect Costs	6,082
TOTAL COSTS	20,227

2 NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

2.2.3 HARC SMO

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	608
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	-
Participant Support Costs	-
Materials and Supplies	-
Publications/Dissemination	10,000
Consulting	3,200
Computer Services	840
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	-
Total direct costs	14,648
Indirect Costs	6,298
TOTAL COSTS	20,946

2.3 ASSP PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Workshop

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	16,595
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	3,154
Participant Support Costs	31,100
Materials and Supplies	250
Publications/Dissemination	7,694
Consulting	2,500
Computer Services	-
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	3,540
Total direct costs	64,833
Indirect Costs	27,878
TOTAL COSTS	92,711

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
Request for Supplemental Funding Year 2, Award OPP-0101279

4 INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletters

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	17,321
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	-
Participant Support Costs	-
Materials and Supplies	100
Publications/Dissemination	31,475
Consulting	-
Computer Services	-
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	-
Total direct costs	<u>48,896</u>
Indirect Costs	<u>21,025</u>
TOTAL COSTS	69,921

4.7 Publication: The Arctic

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	23,909
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	-
Participant Support Costs	-
Materials and Supplies	-
Publications/Dissemination	19,000
Consulting	-
Computer Services	-
Subcontracts	5,000
Other Direct Costs	-
Total direct costs	<u>47,909</u>
Indirect Costs	<u>18,451</u>
TOTAL COSTS	66,359

5 CORE SUPPORT

5.1 Salaries and Fringe Benefits	50,103
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic/foreign)	4,928
Participant Support Costs	-
Materials and supplies	11,375
Publications/Dissemination	-
Consulting	7,750
Computer Services	125
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	3,506
Total direct costs	<u>77,788</u>
Indirect Costs	<u>33,449</u>
TOTAL COSTS	111,236

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
Request for Supplemental Funding Year 2, Award OPP-0101279

<u>TOTAL</u>	
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	117,526
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel	11,236
Participant Support Costs	31,100
Materials and Supplies	11,725
Publications/Dissemination	68,169
Consulting	13,450
Computer Services	965
Subcontracts	5,000
Other Direct Costs	9,046
Total direct costs	<u>268,217</u>
Indirect Costs @ 43%	<u>113,183</u>
Total direct and indirect	<u><u>381,400</u></u>

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 2

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-mos.		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
	CAL	ACAD	SUMR				
1. Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director	2.70	0.00	0.00	\$ 19,188			
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	2.70	0.00	0.00	19,188			
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
2. (7) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	14.70	0.00	0.00	59,759			
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS				0			
4. (0) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS				0			
5. (2) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)				8,109			
6. (0) OTHER				0			
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)				87,056			
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)				30,470			
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)				117,526			
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT				0			
E. TRAVEL				10,645			
1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							
2. FOREIGN				591			
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$ _____				0			
2. TRAVEL _____				20,000			
3. SUBSISTENCE _____				11,100			
4. OTHER _____				0			
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (40)							
TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS				31,100			
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES				11,725			
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION				68,169			
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES				13,450			
4. COMPUTER SERVICES				965			
5. SUBAWARDS				5,000			
6. OTHER				9,046			
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS				108,355			
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)				268,217			
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) Indirect (Rate: 43.0000, Base: 263217)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)				113,183			
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)				381,400			
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.C.6.j.)				0			
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)				\$ 381,400			
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PD NAME Wendy K Warnick				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
		Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG			

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET Cumulative

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-mos.		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
	CAL	ACAD	SUMR	\$		\$	
1. Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director	2.70	0.00	0.00		19,188		
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. () OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00		0		
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	2.70	0.00	0.00		19,188		
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES	0.00	0.00	0.00		0		
2. (7) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	14.70	0.00	0.00		59,759		
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS					0		
4. (0) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS					0		
5. (2) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)					8,109		
6. (0) OTHER					0		
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)					87,056		
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)					30,470		
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)					117,526		
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT					0		
E. TRAVEL					10,645		
1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							
2. FOREIGN					591		
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$ _____					0		
2. TRAVEL _____					20,000		
3. SUBSISTENCE _____					11,100		
4. OTHER _____					0		
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (40)							
TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS					31,100		
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES					11,725		
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION					68,169		
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES					13,450		
4. COMPUTER SERVICES					965		
5. SUBAWARDS					5,000		
6. OTHER					9,046		
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS					108,355		
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)					268,217		
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)					113,183		
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)					381,400		
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.C.6.j.)					0		
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)					\$ 381,400	\$	
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PD NAME Wendy K Warnick				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
		Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG			

C *ELECTRONIC SIGNATURES REQUIRED FOR REVISED BUDGET